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Hypoglycemic effect of Cabernet Sauvignon wine

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There is a growing awareness of the influence of lifestyle and diet on the development of coronary heart disease, atherosclerosis, diabetes, neurodegenerative disorders, ageing and cancer. A market analysis has shown that consumers believe that wine is healthier than other alcoholic beverages¹. Therefore, wine is one of the most popular drinks, which is consumed for hedonistic, but also health reasons. As a part of a broad investigation about the bioactivity of wines from Serbia, the aim of this study was to compare the hypoglycemic effect of wines from Serbia, Macedonia, France and Italy. The inhibition potential of Cabernet Sauvignon wines was evaluated in *in vitro* assays related to the activity of two digestive enzymes involved in carbohydrate metabolism: α -amylase and α -glucosidase². The HPLC-UV/VIS technique was applied to elucidate differences in the phenolic profile of samples. All analysed wines manifested some hypoglycemic potential: IC₅₀ ranged from 2.38 to 5.02 mg/mL (α -amylase) and 0.17 to 1.40 mg/mL (α -glucosidase). Compared with acarbose, a well-known inhibitor of α -amylase and α -glucosidase, all samples had lower activity. The phenolic profile showed a dominance of gallic acid (41.5-103 mg/L) and catechin (22.9-57.6 mg/L). Malvidin-3-*O*-glucoside (5.50-80.0 mg/L) was leading anthocyanin, while the content of resveratrol ranged from 0.80 to 3.70 mg/L. Obtained results showed that Cabernet Sauvignon wines from Serbia have a comparable hypoglycemic effect of renowned European wines, such as French Cabernet Sauvignon.

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